

AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYASIGA OID BO‘LGAN SO‘ZLARINING GRAMMATIK TAHLILI

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Abstract: In this article, we will consider the words related to the field of information technology that are often used in our speech today. Also, the units related to this branch, which is rapidly developing today, are analyzed grammatically and the methods of their formation are revealed through several examples.

Key words: information technology, word formation, method of composition, method of affixation, new meaning.

We know that every word has a base, that is, every language is based on words. Words that we use a lot all the time have their own way of being formed. The methods of word formation are studied in the topic of word formation given in linguistics and modern Uzbek literary language. Through this statement, we will learn more about the formation of information technology words that can be used in our constant speech.

It is no exaggeration to say that in our society, where science and technology are developed, information and computer technology departments are the concepts most often used in everyday life. Because, no matter what sphere of life we take, no matter what actions we perform, we certainly work with information. Nowadays, information technology is an important factor affecting the rapid development of society.

Word formation means creating a word with a new meaning. Word formation occurs through the change of the lexical meaning, and the formed word often moves from one category to another category. Word formation is done in two ways: 1. Affixation and 2. Composition.

The method of affixation is the formation of a new lexical unit by adding a word-forming suffix to the root. The same method of affixation, that is, word

formation, is called derivation in the book "Current Uzbek Literary Language" by R. Saifullayeva. has been studied. In Hamrayev's book "Mother Tongue" word formation was not taken as a specific topic. It is also mentioned in the phonetics section of the word formation topic, as well as in the noun formation section of the noun topic. But even so, if we compare the two books, Hamrayev's book is explained through examples and this topic is covered more widely. In Sayfullayeva, the topic is briefly given and explained in scientific terms. In this article, based on the books and sources of Saifullayeva and Hamrayev, brief information is given about the formation of words related to information technologies, which are often used in our speech today. The internal capabilities of the Uzbek language play a key role in the formation and development of terminological systems. As in all fields, artificial terms in the terminology of information technologies are one of the main sources in the formation and development of the terminology of this field. Word formation means creating a new word.

*Examples of the phenomenon of word formation by the method of affixation:

- affix -cha. In the Uzbek language, the main function of the affix -cha is to make a word that means to make small, caress. Based on the suffix -cha, terms were also created in the field of information technologies. For example: mouse, asterisk, button, baskets, etc. These terms are the hardware names of the computer device. (control with the mouse, press the computer key, create an asterisk)

affix -li. In the field of information technology, terms are formed using the suffix -li. The affix -li serves as an adjective-forming affix in our language and creates a new word (lexeme). For example: laser printer, system block, etc. (A laser printer prints data using dots.) like affix. The affix - is one of the most active affixes. The -like affix is also a word-forming affix and forms an adjective from a noun. For example: modernity, simplicity, freedom. (information technologies based on modernity).

-la affix. For example: code

-a affix. For example: technique

-on affix. For example, an electron

The method of composition is the creation of a new word by joining two or more words. Compound words are formed in this way. Word formation consists of two parts. The first is the forming base, the second is the forming tool (adverb), and the composition of the formation is called the formation (formative word). In

addition, the phenomenon of creating words from one word group to another word group is a source of enrichment of the lexicon in the language.

The phenomenon of word formation in the method of composition:

Infrastructure» infra+ structure is made in the form of noun + noun.

Technopark» in the form of horse+horse

Archive file» in ot+ot format

Trumpet» is in the form of adjective + noun

Electronic communication is in noun + noun form

We will consider the syntactic method of forming terms using modern communication and information technology terms. 1. Combined terms. 2. Combined terms. It can also be said that compound terms are made by the method of composition.

Compound terms are also actively used in the field of information technology terms. When referring to the current terminological systems of science and technology or professions, it is known that compound terms are quantitatively more than single terms. The field of information technology is characterized by a large number of terms consisting of two or three components. For example: automatic system, mathematical model, feedback, etc.

In conclusion, it can be said that nowadays new words are coming in a lot through information technology. We use these words a lot, but we don't know how they are made and in what form. At this point, it should be said that in the creation of terms of modern communication and information technologies, internal sources, that is, methods of word formation, sources other than the vocabulary of the language are widely used.

List of used literature

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